

APPENDIX J

Dialog and Scoring example

Table J.1

Example of messages to related with C1 skill

Turn	Student 1	Student 2	Student 3
1	<i>What stars do we choose?</i>		
1	<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##</i>		
1	<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##. What do you think?</i>		
1	<i>XX select the ## and your ZZ the ##</i>		
1	<i>Select your stars</i>		
2		<i>I think I have a plan.</i>	
2		<i>I do not know which stars we should choose.</i>	
2		<i>Does anyone else know what to choose?</i>	
2		<i>Yes I agree.</i>	
2		<i>I disagree.</i>	
3			<i>I think I have a plan.</i>
3			<i>I think I have a different plan from XX.</i>
3			<i>I do not know which stars we should choose.</i>
3			<i>I agree with XX.</i>
3			<i>I disagree with XX.</i>
4	<i>If we select the stars ##, ## and ##, we form the same objective constellation, because it has the same colors and order.</i>		
4	<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##</i>		
4	<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##. What do you think?</i>		
4	<i>XX select the ## and your ZZ the ##</i>		
4	<i>Do what I said!</i>		
5		<i>If we select the stars ##, ## and ##, we form the same objective constellation, because it has the same colors and order.</i>	
5		<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##</i>	
5		<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##. What do you think?</i>	
5		<i>XX select the ## and your ZZ the ##</i>	
5		<i>I [agree, disagree] with XX.</i>	

6			<i>If we select the stars ##, ## and ##, we form the same objective constellation, because it has the same colors and order.</i>
6			<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##</i>
6			<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##. What do you think?</i>
6			<i>XX select the ## and your ZZ the ##</i>
6			<i>I [agree, disagree] with XX.</i>
7	<i>Yes I agree XX.</i>	<i>Yes I agree XX.</i>	<i>Yes I agree XX.</i>
7	<i>I disagree XX.</i>	<i>I disagree XX.</i>	<i>I disagree XX.</i>

Note: The symbols ## are replaced by a selector in the interface, which allows the user to select a number between 1 to 46, corresponding to the index of the star or atom of which he is speaking. XX, YY, ZZ, are replaced by the interface by the names of student 1, student 2 and student 3 respectively or by the names of the agents in the human-agent version.

Table J.2
Scoring example skill C1, 3 points

Turn	Student 1	Student 2	Student 3
1	<i>What stars do we choose?</i>		
2		<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##. What do you think?</i>	
3			<i>I'm going to choose the ##</i>
4	<i>If we select the stars ##, ## and ##, we form the same objective constellation, because it has the same colors and order.</i>		
5		<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##</i>	
6			<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##</i>
7	<i>Yes, I agree XX.</i>	<i>Yes, I agree XX.</i>	

Table J.3
Scoring example skill C1, 0 points

Turn	Student 1	Student 2	Student 3
1	<i>Select your stars</i>		
2		<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##. What do you think?</i>	
3			<i>I'm going to choose the ##</i>
4	<i>Do what I said!</i>		
5		<i>If we select the stars ##, ## and ##, we form the same objective constellation, because it has the same colors and order.</i>	
6			<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##</i>
7	<i>I do not agree XX.</i>	<i>Yes, I agree XX..</i>	

Note: The symbols ## are replaced by a selector in the interface, which allows the user to select a number between 1 to 46, corresponding to the index of the star or atom of which he is speaking. XX, YY, ZZ, are replaced by the interface by the names of student 1, student 2 and student 3 respectively or by the names of the agents in the human-agent version.